

RIGHTS OF LEGAL ENTITIES AND INDIVIDUALS TO LAND PLOTS**Sa'rsenbaeva Sayora Aymurza qizi**

Karakalpakstan Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnologies

Qallibekova Zulqumar Berdibekovna

Scientific supervisor

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12573335>

Abstract. *In this article, the rights of legal entities and individuals to land plots are specified, as well as the land code of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other legal documents.*

Key words: *Land plot, Land fund, legislation, ownership, cadaster.*

ПРАВА ЮРИДИЧЕСКИХ И ФИЗИЧЕСКИХ ЛИЦ НА ЗЕМЕЛЬНЫЕ УЧАСТКИ

Аннотация. *В данной статье указаны права юридических и физических лиц на земельные участки, а также Земельный кодекс Республики Узбекистан и другие правовые документы.*

Ключевые слова: *Земельный участок, Земельный фонд, законодательство, собственность, кадастр.*

Plot of land. A plot of land is a part of the land fund with a registered border, area, location, legal regime and other characteristics reflected in the state land cadastre. The boundary of the plot of land is noted on the plans (drawings) and determined in kind (on the site itself). The area of the plot of land is determined in kind (in the place itself) after the boundary is determined.

A plot of land can be divided or undivided. Each of the parts that can be divided into parts without changing its main purpose of use and without violating the fire protection, sanitary, environmental, urban planning and other mandatory norms and regulations and formed after the implementation of this work a land plot that can form an independent land plot is a divisible land plot. A land plot that cannot be divided into independent land plots according to the purpose of use is an indivisible land plot. Land ownership in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Land is state property - national wealth, it is necessary to use it wisely, it is protected by the state and cannot be sold, exchanged, gifted, pledged, except for the cases established by the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Rights of legal entities and individuals to land plots.

Legal entities in accordance with the land code of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other legal documents: permanent ownership; continuous use; temporary (temporary) use; rent; they can have land plots on the basis of property rights.

Individuals in accordance with the Land Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other

legal documents: inheritable lifetime ownership; continuous use; temporary (temporary) use; rent; Emergence of property rights to land plots of legal entities and individuals who can own land plots based on property rights. The property rights of legal entities and individuals to land plots are created when trade and service facilities are privatized along with the land plots on which they are located in accordance with the procedure established by law.

Diplomatic missions and equivalent international organizations accredited in the Republic of Uzbekistan have the right of ownership to the land plots, the building or parts of the building they use as the representative office building, including the residence of the head of the mission together with the land plots on which they are located, as well as the construction of the buildings of these representative offices. It is created when the land plots are realized in accordance with the procedure established by law.

Certificates of foreign legal entities and individuals - employees of the diplomatic corps, representatives of the press accredited in the Republic of Uzbekistan, employees of permanent representative offices of companies, companies and international organizations, persons working on a permanent basis in enterprises with foreign investment, as well as permanent residents and residence certificates in the republic The property rights of the persons to the plots of land arise when the residential buildings are realized to them along with the plots of land on which these buildings are located in accordance with the procedure established by law.

Use of plots of land for building construction. Legal and natural persons who take land plots (except for arable land) for permanent ownership and use, inheritable lifetime ownership, long-term temporary use, rent and ownership, in case of fulfillment of obligations regarding the task of maintaining the land plot in accordance with the law has the right to build, demolish or reconstruct enterprises, buildings, constructions in the prescribed manner. Payment for land. A fee is paid for the use of land in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Legal entities and individuals who have land plots in their ownership, use and ownership shall pay a fee for the land. Land tax is paid annually in the form of land tax, the amount of which is determined depending on the quality of the land plot, its location and the level of water supply. When land plots are leased, the land fee is charged in the form of rent, the amount of which is determined according to the agreement of the parties, but it should not be less than one or more than three times the land tax rate, if the land is used for agricultural purposes, the land will be one times the tax rate.

Land allocation documents:

1. Information on the plot of land
2. Decision of the regional governor

3. Decision of the district governor (purchase agreement, gift agreement, inheritance, etc.)
4. Act of the Land Selection Commission
5. Decision of the company, farm or QFY
6. Application of a natural or legal person
7. Extract from the agricultural or urban master plan
8. Topographic plan M 1:500
9. Record of calculation of land types by contours
10. Record of area calculation by coordinates
11. Legal information on the limitation and delimitation of the land plot (Article 32 of Section VI of the Annex to Decision No. 272 of 30.12.2006 of the Cabinet of Ministers)
12. Certificate of on-site measurement of the plot of land and agreement on its boundaries
13. Architectural projects
14. Additional information. Cancellation of rights to land plots.

The right to own the whole plot of land or a part of it, or the right to use it permanently or temporarily, as well as the right to rent a plot of land, will be canceled in the following cases:

- 1) When the plot of land is voluntarily abandoned;
- 2) When the land plot has expired;
- 3) when a legal entity is terminated;
- 4) when the land lease contract is canceled or becomes invalid;
- 5) when the employment relationship, which is the basis for the receipt of the check for use in the service, is canceled, unless otherwise provided for by legislation;
- 6) When the land plot is used for purposes other than those specified;
- 7) When the land plot is not used rationally, it is expressed in the fact that the level of productivity for agricultural land is lower than the norm (according to the cadastral assessment) for three years;
- 8) In the event that the plot of land is used in ways that lead to a decrease in soil fertility, its contamination with chemical and radioactive substances, and deterioration of the ecological situation;
- 9) in case of regular non-payment of land tax within the terms specified by law, as well as rent within the terms specified in the lease agreement; 10) if the plot of land set aside for agricultural needs has not been used for one year, and the plot of land set aside for needs not related to the agricultural sector has not been used for two years;

11) when the land plot has not been used within two years after the purchase of the land plot on the basis of the order giving the right of inheritable lifetime ownership, and in the case of

the right of inheritable lifetime ownership of the land plot, - when it has not been used during the term of the pledge agreement. Unused plots of land will be taken from the previous owners with the price paid by them covered;

12) When the land plot is confiscated in accordance with the procedure stipulated in the Land Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Laws may provide for the right to own plots of land, the right to permanent use of plots of land, and other cases of cancellation of the right to rent plots of land.

Property rights to land plots are canceled in the following cases in accordance with the established procedure:

1) when objects of the trade and service sector, as well as residential buildings and other buildings or a part of buildings are sold together with the plots of land on which these buildings are located; 2) when trade and service sector objects, as well as residential buildings and other buildings or a part of buildings for state and public needs, are repurchased together with the plots of land on which they are located; 3) when objects of the trade and service sector, as well as residential buildings and other buildings or a part of buildings, together with the plots of land on which they are located, are confiscated in the cases specified by law. Termination of the right to own the land plot or the right to permanent or temporary use of the land plot in cases where the right to own the whole plot of land or a part of it, or the right to use it permanently or temporarily, as well as the right to lease the plot of land, are canceled. Land use and protection It is carried out by the decisions of the governors of the relevant districts, cities, regions or by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan based on the documents confirming the validity of the termination of rights in accordance with the submission of the bodies that exercise state control over it. Legal entities and individuals who are dissatisfied with the decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan and these officials to terminate the right to own land plots, the right to permanent or temporary use of land plots, may appeal to the court against these decisions. Termination of the right to own a plot of land or the right to permanent or temporary use of a plot of land shall be carried out in accordance with the procedure established by law. Termination of the lease right to the plot of land is carried out by canceling the lease agreement.

If the owner, user, lessee and owner of the plot of land commits actions that clearly indicate the relinquishment of rights to the plot of land (going abroad, not using the plot of land for a longer period than the specified period), this plot of land is subject to the law is considered as ownerless property according to the procedure established by the documents. Relinquishment of the rights to the plot of land is the obligation of the owner, user, tenant and owner of this plot of land, until the plot of land is transferred to another person, but from the moment of relinquishment or from the

date of state registration as ownerless property. within one year, will not cause cancellation. The right of ownership of all or part of the land area or the procedures for its permanent or temporary use shall be canceled in case of violation. A plot of land or a part of it is taken away for state and public needs with the consent of the owner of the land or in agreement with the user of the land according to the decision of the relevant (within their powers) district, city, regional hokimities, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Also, in other cases of violation of the documents of the Law on Land, the body conducting state control over land protection warns the land owner and user of the land and submits a proposal to the body that granted the land plot to replace the land plot. The body that bought the plot of land makes a decision on repossession within one month. State registration of the right to a plot of land is the entry of the right to a plot of land into the land register by local state authorities. According to Article 35 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the rights of legal entities and individuals to land plots must be entered into the state register. State registration of rights to land plots is carried out at the place where the land plots are located. The following shall be included in the state register:

- information about the person who received the right to the land plot;

- description of the plot of land;

- information on the requirements of the land plot grant agreement, land plot maintenance tasks and servitudes;

- decisions of competent bodies to include a plot of land in the exclusion zone for state or public needs;

- other information specified by law.

State registration of the rights of legal entities and individuals to land plots shall be carried out by the relevant competent body within ten days from the date of receipt of the application with the attached necessary documents on the rights to land plots, except for the cases provided for by law. A certificate stating the date of registration and serial number is issued on the state registration of the rights to land plots.

The following are the grounds for refusing to register the right to a plot of land: - the state registration body has documents proving the existence of a dispute about who owns this plot of land; — the state registration body has information about the seizure of the land in accordance with the procedure established by law. The procedure for state registration of the right to a plot of land is regulated by the Regulation on the procedure for maintaining the State Land Cadastre and the instruction on the procedure for the state registration of rights to plots of land in the Republic of Uzbekistan, approved by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of Uzbekistan No. 543 of December 31, 1998.

REFERENCES

1. Кузибоев Т.К. “Геодезия” “Укитувчи”, Тошкент, 1975.
2. Норхужаев К.Н. “Инженерлик геодезияси”, Тошкент, Укитувчи 1984.
3. Мубораков Х. Геодезия ва картография. Т. Ўқитувчи, 2002й.
4. Назиров А. ГеодезияТошкент “Ўқитувчи”, 1978
5. Яковлев Н.В.Высшая геодезия. Учебник для вузов. – М.Недра, 1989
6. Toshpo'latov S.A., Avchiyev Sh.K., Kovalyov N.V. Oliy geodeziya. Toshkent, 2002.
7. Muborakov H. Ahmedov.Geodeziya va kartografiya. Toshkent "O'qituvchi" 2002.